

Black Mesa Photogrammetry: Apple 4

Processing Report

06 April 2023

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	124	Camera stations:	124
Flying altitude:	1.49 m	Tie points:	58,566
Ground resolution:	0.835 mm/pix	Projections:	155,408
Coverage area:	33 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.436 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
2+ (3.7mm)	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for 2+ (3.7mm).

2+ (3.7mm)

124 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	P1	P2
F	2427	0.14	1.00	0.08	0.04	-0.80	0.10	0.08	0.07	-0.09	0.09	-0.22
Cx	19.2178	0.16		1.00	0.02	-0.08	0.24	0.06	-0.06	0.07	0.91	-0.01
Cy	-6.55694	0.14			1.00	-0.29	0.05	-0.05	-0.03	0.03	0.02	0.79
B1	-29.0199	0.12				1.00	-0.10	-0.12	0.05	-0.04	-0.08	0.10
B2	1.25554	0.095					1.00	0.04	-0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01
K1	-0.00413014	7.9e-05						1.00	-0.94	0.87	0.05	-0.11
K2	0.0129611	0.00017							1.00	-0.98	-0.06	0.00
K3	-0.0144486	0.00012								1.00	0.07	0.01
P1	0.000808393	1.8e-05									1.00	-0.01
P2	0.000507826	1.2e-05										1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
6.10505	4.9193	3.97987	7.84036	8.79265

Table 3. Average camera location error.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 4.93 mm/pix
Point density: 4.11 points/cm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	124
Aligned cameras	124
Coordinate system	WGS 84 (EPSG::4326)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	58,566 of 152,433
RMS reprojection error	0.173889 (0.435831 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.532037 (2.23589 pix)
Mean key point size	2.43846 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	3.37523

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	High
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	Source
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	2 minutes 52 seconds
Matching memory usage	1.01 GB
Alignment time	1 minutes 15 seconds
Alignment memory usage	201.03 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k3, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Optimization time	1 seconds
Date created	2022:10:27 00:56:26
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	9.64 MB

Depth Maps

Count	123
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	16 minutes 24 seconds
Memory usage	2.09 GB
Date created	2022:10:27 01:27:38
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	483.40 MB

Dense Point Cloud

Points	45,969,354
Point colors	3 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	High
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Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	16 minutes 24 seconds
Memory usage	2.09 GB
Dense cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	29 minutes 0 seconds
Memory usage	5.24 GB
Date created	2022:10:27 01:56:38
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	687.06 MB
Model	
Faces	3,381,569
Vertices	1,692,179
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	High
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	16 minutes 24 seconds
Memory usage	2.09 GB
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	23 minutes 1 seconds
Memory usage	6.95 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	3 minutes 30 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	3.02 GB
Blending time	3 minutes 52 seconds
Blending memory usage	1.91 GB
Blending GPU memory usage	952.80 MB
Date created	2022:10:27 02:22:55
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	170.02 MB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.0 build 13794
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	31.85 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-6920HQ CPU @ 2.90GHz
GPU(s)	Quadro M2200